

EOMORES

D6.4 operational service delivery

WP6 –Operational service delivery

Authors: Lazaros Spaias (WI), Annelies Hommersom (WI), Mark Warren (PML), Saku Anttila (SYKE), Jenni Attila (SYKE), Sampsa Koponen (SYKE)

TARTU OBSERVATORY
space research centre

KLAIPĖDA
UNIVERSITY

UNIVERSITY of
STIRLING

PML

Plymouth Marine
Laboratory

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730066

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	730066	Acronym	EOMORES	
Full Title	Earth Observation-Based Services For Monitoring And Reporting Of Ecological Status			
Horizon 2020 Call	EO-1-2016: Downstream applications			
Type of Action	Innovation Action			
Start Date	01/12/2016	Duration	36 months	
Project URL	http://eomores-h2020.eu			
EU Project Officer	Iulia SIMION			
Project Coordinator	Water Insight BV			
Deliverable	D6.4 operational service delivery			
Work Package	WP6 – Operational service delivery			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	M36	Actual	M36
Nature	O – Other	Dissemination Level	PU - Public	
Lead Beneficiary	Water Insight			
Lead Author	Lazaros Spaias	Email	spaias@waterinsight.nl	
	Water Insight	Phone	+31 317 210004	
Other authors	Lazaros Spaias (WI), Annelies Hommersom (WI), Mark Warren (PML), Saku Anttila (SYKE), Jenni Attila (SYKE), Sampsa Koponen (SYKE)			
Reviewer(s)	Miguel Dionisio (Deltares)			
Keywords	Earth Observation, processing, operational,			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
1.0	22/10/2019	Template		WI
2.0	13/11/2019	Draft	Additions for all services	PML, SYKE, Deltares
3.0	22/11/2019	Final	Review by Deltares and additions by KU	Deltares

How to cite this document:

Please use the following reference when citing this report:

Lazaros Spaias (WI), Annelies Hommersom (WI), Mark Warren (PML), Saku Anttila (SYKE), Jenni Attila (SYKE), Sampsa Koponen (SYKE), 2019. D6.4 Operational service delivery, EOMORES Project Deliverable. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3987951

Table of Contents

- I. Introduction 5
 - I.1. Scope..... 5
- II. Operational service delivery 6
 - II.1. Services for: ARPA Umbria 6
 - II.2. Services for: ARPA Lombardia 7
 - II.3. Services for: Lithuanian EPA..... 9
 - II.4. Services for: Nature Research Center 10
 - II.5. Services for: Monitor2020 10
 - II.6. Services for: Finnish Environmental authorities (represented by SYKE) 11
 - II.7. Services for: SEPA..... 12
 - II.8. Services for: UK EA 13
 - II.9. Services for: Centre of Limnology 14
 - II.10. Services for: Natuurmonumenten 15
 - II.11. Services for: water authority HHNK..... 16
 - II.12. Services for: water authority NZV..... 17
- III. The future 19

Table of Figures

- Figure 1 EOMORES service setup..... 6
- Figure 2 Example of the high-frequent and spatial algae bloom monitoring services ARPA Umbria. The time series are also combined with model forecasts 7
- Figure 3 Overview of the water quality mapping services provided to ARPA Lombardia 8
- Figure 4 Example of a water quality time series and mapping service provided to ARPA Lombardia... 8
- Figure 5 Example of the high-frequent and spatial cyanobacteria monitoring services provided to EPA Lithuania 9
- Figure 6 Example of the in situ and earth observation based services provided to Nature Research Center..... 10
- Figure 7 Continuing and spatially encompassing water quality estimations from a coastal WFD water body presented as animations in the Tarkka-service (www.syke.fi/tarkka ; under animations). Spatially and temporally complete estimations from a single year were calculated with data fusion 11
- Figure 8 Example from water quality statistics view provided by the STATUS service from a WFD water body. STATUS shows statistics, distributions and time series of observations by all available data sources within WFD areas in Finland. The service is currently used by the Finnish Environmental Authorities 12
- Figure 9 Example of the lake turbidity product made available to the Scottish Environmental Protection Agency..... 13

Figure 10 Example of annual turbidity 50th percentile product service for the UK Environmental Agency..... 14

Figure 11 Example of the water quality service for the Center of Limnology, showing the distribution and time series of coloured dissolved organic matter 15

Figure 12 Example of the site-characterization services provided to Natuurmonumenten, showing the spatial effects of the construction of the MarkerWadden islands on transparency..... 16

Figure 13 Example of the Algae Radar algal bloom forecasting service as provided to local water authority HHNK..... 17

Figure 14 Example of the scum forecasting service (EWACS) as it is running within the data management system (Delft-FEWS) of water authority Noorderzijlvest 18

Figure 15 Example of the WFD classified mapping service (based on phytoplankton abundance from satellite imagery) within the in-house data management system (Delft-FEWS) of water authority Noorderzijlvest..... 18

I. Introduction

EOMORES develops new efficient information services to support international, national and regional authorities responsible for monitoring, management and reporting of water quality as well as private entities dealing with water quality such as dredging companies. These services, based on the integration of Earth Observation (EO), autonomous optical in situ sensors and ecological modelling, will be fully automated, commercial, reliable and sustainable. The validated data from the three components can be flexibly combined into higher-level products to fit the users' information needs.

In Work Package 2 the details of the services to be developed were defined in close cooperation with users in the User Board. The technical implementation plan (D2.4) concentrated on the software infrastructure for the operational delivery of the EOMORES services. It gives an overview of the individual service components as well as the overall service infrastructure.

First, the components of the EOMORES services were further developed: the EO based processors and products (D3.3), the automated in situ instruments setup, prototype processors and products (D3.4), and the improved version of the algal forecasting models (D3.5). Based on these, the higher-level products and indicators were developed (D4.1).

D6.2, the System readiness report, listed which services are 'ready for use', i.e. operational. For EOMORES, this means that if a new user contacts us and requests an EOMORES related service, then we will be in a secure position to start-up the service and deliver it according to the users' requirements, in a financially viable way.

The real 'deliverable' of the EOMORES "Operational service delivery" are the services itself. The purpose of this document is to provide an impression of this actual operational service delivery.

I.1. Scope

This document provides an impression of the EOMORES services.

II. Operational service delivery

The general service scheme within EOMORES is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 EOMORES service setup

To be able to respond in a timely manner to user requests, provide large volumes of data and to be financially viable, manual tasks need to be avoided for an efficient and effective operational service. Practically, this means that most of the EOMORES services need to be automated to a large extent to qualify as an operational service.

The technical details of the service provision are described in D6.2: System readiness report. D6.2 describes the setup of the Earth Observation (EO) based product line, the in situ WISPstation measurement and data processing line and the ecological models production line.

Most EOMORES services have been operational during spring, summer and autumn 2019: the bathing water season, the period during which algae bloom, the Water Framework Directive (WFD) requires monitoring and during which the EOMORES users require data. In the next sections an overview of the provided services is presented.

II.1. Services for: ARPA Umbria

Institutional name of user: **Regional Agency for Environmental Protection, Regione Umbria**

Country: Italy

Algorithms selected, built and/or tuned by: CNR-IREA

Service components: EO-based maps, high-frequent in situ WISPstation data, AlgaeRadar model forecasts (using the in situ optical measurements as input)

Operational services by: WI, Deltares

Validation by: CNR-IREA

Examples/screenshots/photo's:

This project is co-funded by the European Union

Figure 2 Example of the high-frequent and spatial algae bloom monitoring services ARPA Umbria. The time series are also combined with model forecasts

The services of ARPA Umbria consist of maps of Chlorophyll-a and surface temperature based on satellite data from the Sentinel-3 satellite, high-frequent in situ data measured by a WISPstation, and forecasts of algal blooms by the AlgaeRadar model. The WISPstation provides real time measures of Chlorophyll-a, phycocyanin, suspended matter and the diffuse attenuation coefficient; its chlorophyll concentrations are used to feed into the AlgaeRadar model. The optical methods were defined and validated by CNR-IREA. The operational provision of the mapping and in-situ WISPstation services is run by Water Insight via the [EOMORES portal](#). The algal bloom forecasting service is performed by Deltares.

II.2. Services for: ARPA Lombardia

Institutional name of user: **Regional Agency for Environmental Protection, Regione Lombardia**

Country: Italy

Algorithms selected, built and/or tuned by: CNR-IREA

Service components: EO-based maps

Operational services by: WI

Validation by: CNR-IREA

Examples/screenshots/photo's:

This project is co-funded by the European Union

Figure 3 Overview of the water quality mapping services provided to ARPA Lombardia

ARPA Lombardia receives satellite based maps of a range of parameters and different satellite data sources (Sentinel-2, Sentinel-3 and Landsat 8) for a couple of lakes in their area via the [EOMORES portal](#). The portal allows the user to zoom and make time series.

Figure 4 Example of a water quality time series and mapping service provided to ARPA Lombardia

The algorithms have been defined and the results have been validated by CNR-IREA. The operational service is provided by Water Insight.

II.3. Services for: Lithuanian EPA

Institutional name of user: **Marine Research Department, Environmental Protection Agency**

Country: Lithuania

Algorithms selected, built and/or tuned by: KU

Service components: EO-based maps, in situ WISPstation measurements

Operational services by: WI

Validation by: KU

Examples/screenshots/photo's:

Figure 5 Example of the high-frequent and spatial cyanobacteria monitoring services provided to EPA Lithuania

Maps of Chlorophyll-a, suspended matter and surface temperature are provided to EPA for the area of the Curonian Lagoon, for suspended matter and surface temperature also for the Lithuanian Baltic Sea coastal waters. The maps are based on satellite data from Sentinel-2, Sentinel-3, Landsat 8 and GHRSS (group for high resolution sea surface temperature). Within the Lagoon there are two WISPstations installed that provide real time measures of chlorophyll-a, phycocyanin, suspended matter and the diffuse attenuation coefficient. The data is validated by the University of Klaipeda, and provided in an operational mode via the [EOMORES portal](#) by Water Insight.

This project is co-funded by the European Union

II.4. Services for: Nature Research Center

Institutional name of user: **Nature Research Center, Laboratory of Algology and Microbial Ecology (NRC)**

Country: Lithuania

Algorithms selected, built and/or tuned by: KU

Service components: EO-based maps, in situ WISPstation measurements

Operational services by: WI

Validation by: KU

Examples/screenshots/photo's:

Figure 6 Example of the in situ and earth observation based services provided to Nature Research Center

Suspended matter, Chlorophyll-a and surface temperature are mapped for the Curonian Lagoon. The maps are based on satellite data from Sentinel-2, Sentinel-3, Landsat 8 and GRSSST. Data from the two WISPstations that are installed within the Lagoon provide real time measures of chlorophyll-a, phycocyanin, suspended matter and the diffuse attenuation coefficient. The data is validated by the University of Klaipeda and provided to NRC in operational modus by Water Insight, via the [EOMORES portal](#).

II.5. Services for: Monitor2020

Institutional name of user: **National environment monitoring strategy & development program**

Country: Finland

Algorithms selected, built and/or tuned by: SYKE, Finnish Meteorological Institute, University of Helsinki

This project is co-funded by the European Union

Service components: Higher level products

Operational services by: SYKE

Validation by: SYKE

Examples/screenshots/photo's:

Figure 7 Continuing and spatially encompassing water quality estimations from a coastal WFD water body presented as animations in the Tarkka-service (www.syke.fi/tarkka ; under animations). Spatially and temporally complete estimations from a single year were calculated with data fusion

EOMORES provided EO based modelled spatial representativeness information for the Data fusion project under the MONITOR2020 program. This information was used in combining different data sources into spatially and temporally comprehensive water quality products. These results were also included in the SYKE's [EOMORES service](#) (under animations in the service).

II.6. Services for: Finnish Environmental authorities (represented by SYKE)

Institutional name of user: **Finnish Environmental Institute representing regional environmental authorities**

Country: Finland

Algorithms selected, built and/or tuned by: SYKE

This project is co-funded by the European Union

Service components: Higher level products

Operational services by: SYKE

Validation by: SYKE

Examples/screenshots/photo's:

Figure 8 Example from water quality statistics view provided by the STATUS service from a WFD water body. STATUS shows statistics, distributions and time series of observations by all available data sources within WFD areas in Finland. The service is currently used by the Finnish Environmental Authorities

The STATUS web service shows statistics, distributions and time series of observations by all available data sources within WFD areas in Finland. The colours above and below the histogram show the WFD class boundary limits. The STATUS service is currently open for the Finnish environmental authorities conducting national WFD reporting. Through this service the authorities responsible for the assessment have access to water quality products from approximately 40% of Finnish lake and almost all coastal water bodies. STATUS is directly linked to the national water body information system used by the authorities in WFD classification.

II.7. Services for: SEPA

Institutional name of user: **Scottish Environment Protection Agency**

Country: UK

Algorithms selected, built and/or tuned by: USTIR, PML

Service components: EO-based maps, higher-level products, for one year: high-frequent in situ WISPstation measurements

Operational services by: PML

Validation by: USTIR

This project is co-funded by the European Union

Examples/screenshots/photo's:

Figure 9 Example of the lake turbidity product made available to the Scottish Environmental Protection Agency

EOMORES provides 5-day aggregated turbidity products from the Sentinel-2 satellite and 1-day aggregated turbidity products from the Sentinel-3 satellite via PML's [EOMORES portal](#). The whole UK and Ireland coastal and inland region is covered. Annual 10th, 50th and 90th percentile maps of Sentinel-2 turbidity are also provided.

II.8. Services for: UK EA

Institutional name of user: **UK Environment Agency**

Country: UK

Algorithms selected, built and/or tuned by: USTIR, PML

Service components: EO-based maps

Operational services by: PML

Validation by: USTIR

Examples/screenshots/photo's:

This project is co-funded by the European Union

Figure 10 Example of annual turbidity 50th percentile product service for the UK Environmental Agency

EOMORES provides 5-day aggregated turbidity products from the Sentinel-2 satellite and 1-day aggregated turbidity products from the Sentinel-3 satellite via PML's [EOMORES portal](#). The whole UK and Ireland coastal and inland region is covered. Annual 10th, 50th and 90th percentile maps of Sentinel-2 turbidity are also provided.

II.9. Services for: Centre of Limnology

Institutional name of user: **Centre of Limnology**

Country: Estonia

Algorithms selected, built and/or tuned by: TO

Service components: EO-based maps, high-frequent in situ WISPstation measurements

Operational services by: WI

Validation by: TO

Examples/screenshots/photo's:

This project is co-funded by
the European Union

Figure 11 Example of the water quality service for the Center of Limnology, showing the distribution and time series of coloured dissolved organic matter

The Center of Limnology of Estonia receives water quality mapping services of coloured dissolved organic matter, diffuse light attenuation coefficient (Kd) and chlorophyll-a for various lakes in the country via the [EOMORES portal](#). The products are based on Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 satellite data. A WISPstation in situ instrument has also been installed in one of the lakes, which provides high-frequency measurements of Kd, chlorophyll-a, phycocyanin and total suspended matter. The services are provided by Water Insight and validated by Tartu Observatory.

II.10. Services for: Natuurmonumenten

Institutional name of user: **Vereniging Natuurmonumenten**

Country: Netherlands

Algorithms selected, built and/or tuned by: WI

Service components: EO-based maps

Operational services by: WI

Validation by: Netherlands Institute for Ecology (NIOO-KNAW) and WI

Examples/screenshots/photo's:

This project is co-funded by the European Union

Figure 12 Example of the site-characterization services provided to Natuurmonumenten, showing the spatial effects of the construction of the MarkerWadden islands on transparency

For monitoring the effect of construction works and the newly built islands on the water quality, EOMORES provides maps of Secchi disk depth, total suspended matter and chlorophyll-a, via the [EOMORES portal](#). The maps are based on data from the Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 satellites. The Netherlands Institute for Ecology (NIOO-KNAW) is involved in the validation of the products, the service is provided by Water Insight.

II.11. Services for: water authority HHNK

Institutional name of user: **Water Authority Hoogheemraadschap Hollands Noorderkwartier (HHNK)**

Country: Netherlands

Algorithms selected, built and/or tuned by: n/a

Service components: AlgaeRadar model

Operational services by: Deltares

Validation by: Deltares

Examples/screenshots/photo's:

Figure 13 Example of the Algae Radar algal bloom forecasting service as provided to local water authority HHNK

water board Hoogheemraadschap Hollands Noorderkwartier (HHNK) needs information on future harmful algal blooms at the several beaches in lake 't Twiske (NL). For this, they will use the AlgaeRadar that has been setup for the different bathing water locations at the lake. The model provides a forecast for the whole bathing water season that will be updated as soon as new in situ measurements are available. Employees of the water board received training from Deltares on the model and will operate the forecasts themselves, and Deltares will provide support as a service.

II.12. Services for: water authority NZV

Institutional name of user: **Local Water Authority Noorderzijlvest (NZV)**

Country: Netherlands

Algorithms selected, built and/or tuned by: WI

Service components: EO-based maps, in situ optical measurements, EWACS model (based on Delft3D), AlgaeRadar model (using the in situ optical measurements as input), higher-level products (maps of WFD classes)

Operational services by: WI, Deltares

Validation by: WI

Examples/screenshots/photo's:

This project is co-funded by the European Union

Figure 14 Example of the scum forecasting service (EWACS) as it is running within the data management system (Delft- FEWS) of water authority Noorderzijlvest

The services for water authority Noorderzijlvest are implemented within their data management system (FEWS). EOMORES Earth observation-based maps, model forecasts and in situ data can be combined with their other data sources.

Figure 15 Example of the WFD classified mapping service (based on phytoplankton abundance from satellite imagery) within the in-house data management system (Delft-FEWS) of water authority Noorderzijlvest

III. The future

After one season of operational service provision as presented in this document, the EOMORES partners and users are having one-to-one meetings to evaluate the services and discuss the future. The provided services are accessed at all levels: product quality, product fitness for purpose, service quality and utility. Also, the users' interest in continuation of the services on a commercial basis is discussed. The results of the evaluation will be described in D5.3 Final validation report. The users' interest for the future, including proposed additional services will be described in D2.6 Final user requirements document and validation plan. Potential commercial contracts will be listed in D7.7 Final update of SLAs with users.

